

LAND USE AND CROPPING PATTERN CHANGE IN BAREILLY DISTRICT OF UP: A GEOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Land use pattern of a region refers to the way the land of any region is utilized. The land may be used for agriculture, forest, pasture, etc. Many factors like relief, climate and soil as well as social, economic, political conditions of a region determine the land use of a region. The land use analysis is an important aspect of geographical studies which provides proper guidelines for regional planning and development and also for future orientation of agriculture. Cropping Pattern describes the proportion of area under different crops at a point of time in a region. The cropping pattern in any area is affected by a host of physical and human factors. The main objective of the study is to find out the change of land use and cropping pattern in Bareilly district. The present study is based on secondary data. This data has been collected from the District Agriculture Office and District Statistical Handbook for the year 1994-95 to 2016-17. The data has been analyzed in an excel sheet and ArcGIS 10.5 software is used for showing block-wise variation in land use change in the study area. In the study area, Forest cover, Other Uncultivable Waste Land and Net sown area are increasing but area under Fallow land and Area not unavailable for cultivation have decreased. The area under cash crops is increasing but the area under food grains (except wheat) and vegetables are decreasing.

Key words : Land use, agriculture, Bareilly district, Cropping pattern, Cultivated area.

Introduction

Land use is a combination of physical, chemical and biological order and processes on one hand whereas human and social processes on the other (Fazal, 2001). Land use is a series of operation on land, carried out by human beings with the intention to obtain products and benefits. Human use of land varies with the purpose it serves as well as the bio-physical characteristics of the land itself and it, therefore, reflected in the form of land-use (Theobald, 2001). Land use in any region of the world varies due to the variations in the distribution of sunshine, rainfall, the topography of the land, drainage conditions, and soil characteristics. Cropping pattern refers to the proportion of area under various crops at a point of time. Cropping pattern is a dynamic concept it changes over space and time. The cropping pattern of a region is closely influenced by the geo-climatic, socio-cultural, economic, historical and political factors (Husain M., 1996). In any region, the cropping pattern is influenced by rainfall, climatic conditions, temperature, soil type and technology of the area. It is also determined by farmer's decision governed by various factors such as productivity, expected profit, input resources, etc. The nature and intensity of land use are closely related to the technology adopted by man. Extension of agriculture land with the help of technology may cause considerable changes in land use. The demands for new uses of land may be inspired by a technological change or by a change in the size composition and requirements of a community. Some changes are short linked whereas others are more constant. Rapid population increase is also responsible for a

major shift in the land use and cropping pattern of an area because rapid population growth means more demand for food and raw materials for industries. So the land use planning must be in accordance with the changing needs of the population (Singh, et.al, 2005).

Objectives

1. To find out the block-wise variations in land use pattern.
2. To study the change in cropping pattern in the study area.

Limitation

This study focuses only total rural reported area of Bareilly district.

Data Source and Methodology

The study is primarily based on secondary data sources mainly obtained from District Statistical Handbook of Bareilly District, published by Economic and Statistics Division, State Planning Institute, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh. Land use change has been analyzed by block-level considering the data of 1993-94 to the 2016-17 year and the land use categories are based on the census classification. The data has been classified and tabulated in Microsoft Excel. For cartographic mapping ArcGIS 10.5 software is used. Block-wise proportion of area under different land use categories has been calculated and shown on the map with the help of pie diagrams for both the time periods.

Study Area

Bareilly district is the area that has been proposed as a study area for this research work. It is a part of the Rohilkhand region and is located in the northern part of Uttar Pradesh. The district lies between 28°01'N to 28°54'N latitude and 78°58'E to 97°47'E longitude and occupies an area of 4120 km². The whole district is bounded by Uttarakhand state from north, Rampur district from the west, Badaun district from the south and by Pilibhit district from the east. The entire district has been divided into six tehsils with 15 Community Development blocks. During 1994-95 the

Fig. 1: Location aspect of Bareilly District

rural area occupied 98.23 percent of total district and only 2.44 percent area was under urban area which was increased to 2.70 percent in 2016-17 and rural area in district decreased to 97.3 percent. According to 2011, Census of India the total population of Bareilly District is 44, 48,358. Bareilly has a sex ratio of 887 females for every 1000 males. The average literacy rate in Bareilly district as per census of India is 58.49% where male and female literacy is 67.50% and 48.30% respectively.

Classification of Land use

Land use classifications are the systematic arrangement of land on the basis of certain similar characteristics mainly to identify and understand their fundamental utilities intelligently and effectively. Census of India has classified land utilization into nine different categories, but in the present study these have been grouped into five major land use categories as the percentage of area under individual categories is relatively insignificant [Indian Agriculture in brief (1997-98 edition), Directorate of Economics and Statistic]. On the basis of the statistical data abstracted from the sources referred, Bareilly district may be divided into five major land use categories. 1. The area under forest cover, 2. The area is not available for cultivation 3. Other uncultivated waste land excluding fallow land, 4. Fallow land and 5. Net sown area. In overall Land use pattern of Bareilly district in 2016-17, forest land had occupied 0.07 percent, area not available for cultivation 13.01 percent, other uncultivable waste land constituted 2.98 percent, fallow land 2.04 percent and net sown area covered 81.90 percent area of total reporting area (Table:1).

Table 1. Bareilly District, Land use Pattern in– 1994-95 to 2016-17

Sr. No	Land use category	1994-95		2016-17		Changes (%)
		Area (hec.)	Area (%)	Area (hec.)	Area (%)	
1.	Forest cover	235	0.06	291	0.07	0.01
2.	Area not available for cultivation	53653	13.49	51492	13.01	-0.48
3.	Other Uncultivable Waste Land excluding fallow land	6214	1.56	11811	2.98	1.42
4.	Fallow land	15715	3.96	8075	2.04	-1.92
5.	Net sown area	321777	80.92	324242	81.90	0.98
	Total Rural Reported area	397630	100	395911	100	-

Source: Computed from District Statistical Handbook, Bareilly District. U. P., 1994-95 to 2016-17.

Blockwise Land use pattern in Bareilly District

The land use pattern in Bareilly District differs from block to block due to the locality, physical and socio-economic condition. There is a change in physiography, soil types, rainfall, and geology. All these factors played an important role in land use pattern.

Table: 2. Block wise Land use pattern in 1994-95.

Sl. No.	Development Block	Total area	Fallow land		Area not available for Cultivation		Other Uncultivable waste land		Net sown area	
		(hect.)	(hect.)	(%)	(hect.)	(%)	(hect.)	(%)	(hect.)	(%)
1.	Baheri	41356	494	1.19	5602	13.55	162	0.39	35098	84.87
2.	Shergarh	27257	544	2.00	3613	13.26	227	0.83	22873	83.92
3.	Richha	26584	264	0.99	3284	12.35	115	0.43	22 921	86.22
4.	Meerganj	23475	1341	5.71	4709	20.06	332	1.41	17093	72.81
5.	Fatehganj West	18049	1131	6.27	2858	15.83	519	2.88	13541	75.02
6.	Bhojipura	19313	558	2.89	2485	12.87	228	1.18	16042	83.06
7.	Kyara	17551	1687	9.61	5567	31.72	309	1.76	9988	56.91
8.	Ramnagar	22721	1042	4.59	2183	9.61	586	2.58	18910	83.23
9.	Majhgawan	30249	1732	5.73	2829	9.35	578	1.91	25110	83.01
10.	Alampur Jafarabad	28055	1219	4.35	3774	13.45	801	2.86	22170	79.02
11.	Bithiri Chainpur	22121	967	4.37	2798	12.65	298	1.35	18058	81.63
12.	Nawabganj	33682	682	2.02	3960	11.76	363	1.08	28675	85.13
13.	Bhadpura	23428	930	3.97	2671	11.40	356	1.52	19471	83.11
14.	Bhuta	32816	1112	3.39	3046	9.28	771	2.35	27886	84.98
15.	Faridpur	30973	2048	6.61	4274	13.80	569	1.84	23941	77.30
	Total Rural reported area	397630	15751	3.96	53653	13.49	6214	1.56	321777	80.92

Source: Computed from District Statistical Handbook, Bareilly District 1994-95, Uttar Pradesh

1) The area under forest cover

This category denotes the legal states of the land as forest as per the government records. In Bareilly district area under this category has increased from 235 hectares to 291 hectares (1994-2016). Not All but some development blocks record positive changes in this land use category. The area under forest cover has increased due to some measures taken by the government to prevent deforestation to maintain ecological balance. Awareness among the people also plays an important role in the increase in afforestation.

2) Area not available for cultivation

This land use category includes two types of lands (1) the land put non-agricultural use - this type of land is not used in cultivation but considered to be arable land. These types of land are used for settlement purposes, factories, roads, canals, and reservoirs, etc. (2) Barren and uncultivable land – this type of land includes all types of land which is unproductive and virtually

unfit for cultivation. In Bareilly district 1994-95 the area not available for cultivation was 53,653 hectares which was 13.49 % of the total rural reported area but in 2016-17 it is 51,492 hectares (13.01 %). This land use category recorded slight decrease with -0.48 percent in the study area. During 1994-95 highest area under this land use category is found in Baheri block 5602 hectares and lowest was in Ramnagar block with 2183 hectares, while in 2016-17 the highest area not under this category found in Faridpur block 6144 hectares and lowest in Majhgaon 1300 hectares.

3) Other Uncultivable Waste land (Excluding Follow Land)

This category includes (1) barren cultivated wasteland- the land under this category can be used for cultivation but they remain as wasteland for several reasons like floods and erosion, poor drainage system, scarcity of water, etc. (2) Pasture- pasture land includes all permanent or non-permanent grazing land. (3) The area under a bush, forest, and garden- it includes all cultivable land, which is not included in the net sown area but is put to some other agricultural uses like growing forest like, Mango, Sheesham, Babul, etc. In Bareilly district, the other uncultivable land was 6214 hectares (1.56 %) in 1994-95 but it is 11811 hectares (2.98%) in 2016-17. The highest land in this category in the study area was found in Alampur Jafrabad block (801 hectares) and lowest in Richha block (115 hectares) during 1994-94, while in 2016-17 in this category highest area are found Kyara block (1793 hectares) and lowest in Baheri block (231 hectares).

Fig. 2

4) Fallow Land

Fallow land means a piece of land that is normally used for farming in the past but now that is left with no crops on it for a season in order to let it recover its fertility. This land use category includes “Current fallow land” and “Other fallow land”. Current fallow lands include all lands, which is left unsown during the current agricultural year to allow them to regain fertility and also that which remained uncultivated in the short term so that it will retain moisture. Other fallow land includes all land which was taken up for cultivation but is temporary out of cultivation for a period for more than one year but less than five years. In this study both the sub-categories are grouped

Table 3. Block Wise Land use pattern in Bareilly district, 2016-17

Sl. No.	Development Block	Total area	Fallow land		Area not available for Cultivation		Other Uncultivated waste land		Net sown area	
		(hect.)	(hect.)	(%)	(hect.)	(%)	(hect.)	(%)	(hect.)	(%)
1.	Baheri	39800	147	0.37	4848	12.18	231	0.58	34574	86.87
2.	Shergarh	27063	355	1.31	4438	16.40	479	1.77	21790	80.52
3.	Richha	26567	117	0.44	4830	18.18	634	2.39	20986	78.99
4.	Meerganj	22803	408	1.79	2964	13.00	1322	5.80	18107	79.41
5.	Fatehganj West	17498	344	1.97	2739	15.65	652	3.73	13763	78.65
6.	Bhojipura	19121	214	1.12	3068	16.05	524	2.74	15313	80.08
7.	Kyara	16247	1224	7.53	2388	14.70	1793	11.04	10842	66.73
8.	Ramnagar	22452	315	1.40	2217	9.87	681	3.03	19237	85.68
9.	Majhgawan	30278	477	1.58	1300	4.29	766	2.53	27734	91.60
10.	Alampur Jafarabad	27326	603	2.21	2348	8.59	686	2.51	23594	86.34
11.	Bithiri Chainpur	23059	426	1.85	2272	9.85	818	3.55	19543	84.75
12.	Nawabganj	32783	505	1.54	4130	12.60	747	2.28	27398	83.57
13.	Bhadpura	23498	621	2.64	2242	9.54	493	2.10	20141	85.71
14.	Bhuta	34966	1146	3.28	5564	15.91	862	2.47	27392	78.34
15.	Faridpur	32450	1173	3.61	6144	18.93	1123	3.46	23828	73.43
	Total Rural reported area	395911	8075	2.04	51492	13.01	11811	2.98	324242	81.90

Source: Computed from District Statistical Handbook, Bareilly District 2016-17, Uttar Pradesh.

together. In Bareilly district, this land use category includes 15751 hectares in 1993-94 but it has decreased to 8075 hectares in 2016-17. The highest land in this category in Bareilly district is found in Faridpur block (2048 hectares) and lowest in Richha block (264 hectares) during 1994-95, while in 2016-17 in this category highest area is found in Kyara block (1224 hectares) and lowest in Shergarh block (117 hectares).

5) Net sown area

This category represents the total area sown with crops and orchards. In this category area sowed more than once in the same year is counted only once. In Bareilly district, this land use type is high as compared to other land use type because of the upper Ganga plain which is suitable for agriculture. It covered 80.92 percent of total rural reported land in 1994-95 and 81.90 percent in 2016-17 with slight increase. The highest land in this category in the study area was found in Baheri block (35098 hectares) and lowest in Kyara block (9988 hectares) during 1994-

95, while in 2016-17 in this category highest area has been found in Baheri block (34574 hectares) and lowest in Kyara block (10842 hectares).

Cropping pattern

Fig. 3

Table: 4. Temporal changes in cropping pattern in Bareilly District, 2005-06 to 2015-16

Sl. No.	Crop	2005-06		2015-16		Changes (%)
		(Hect.)	(%)	(Hect.)	(%)	
1.	Rice	177119	33.31	168863	31.04	-2.27
2.	Wheat	194880	36.65	206549	37.96	1.31
3.	Barley	72	0.01	29	0.005	-.005
4.	The tide	289	0.05	55	0.01	-0.04
5.	Millet	9412	1.77	8535	1.56	-0.21
6.	Maize	379	0.07	246	0.04	-0.03
7.	Total pulses	17059	3.21	13400	2.46	-0.75
8.	Total oil seeds	21650	4.07	15341	2.81	-1.26
9.	Sugarcane	72233	13.58	87847	16.15	2.57
10.	Total vegetables	18345	3.45	11079	2.04	-1.41
11.	Fodder and miscellaneous	20193	3.80	32068	5.89	2.09
	Total cropped area	531753	-	544061	-	-

Source: Computed from District Statistical Handbook, Bareilly District, U. P., 2005-06 to 2015-16.

Cropping pattern shows the distribution of crops of a region at a point of time. In Bareilly district various crops like Rice, wheat, barley, maize, millets, oil seeds, vegetables, and Fodder crops are sown. Some crops cultivated in large and some crops are in small area. Table 4 shows the changing of cropping pattern in Bareilly district.

Rice

Rice is one of the major crops in India. It is an important food crop and its production act as a staple food for a highly populated country like India. In Bareilly district, it occupied about 31.04% area of the district. Rice has a high nutritive value. It needs the temperature of 21°C during sowing and 37°C during harvesting, it also requires good rainfall and assured irrigation facilities. In the study area, the cultivated area under rice is decreasing. The cultivated area under rice was 177199 hectares (33.31%) during 2005-06 which has decreased to 168863 hectares (31.045) in 2015-16. The change in Land use area is decreasing under rice crops because of lack in irrigation facilities and in place of rice crop, sugarcane and other cash crop has taken place.

Wheat

Wheat is one of the oldest and most important food crops in the world. It is cultivated on more land in the world as well in India than any other food crop. Mid Ganga region is the major productive area of wheat because of suitable climatic conditions for it. During sowing time wheat requires 100- 150°C temperature and at the time of harvesting, it needs 21-27°C temperatures. Wheat is generally sown in November and is harvested in March. The cultivated area under wheat is 194880 hectares (36.65%) in 2005-06 which has increased to 206549 hectares (37.96%) in 2015-16. There is a steady increase in cultivated area under wheat crop reported.

Fig. 4

Millet

Millets are some of the oldest cultivated crops in the world. It is widely grown around the world as cereal crops or grains for fodder and human food. This crop is grown on all types of soil. The cultivated area under millet crop was 9412 (1.77%) hectares in 2005-06 which decreased to 8535 hectares (1.56%) in 2015-16. It has recorded a (-0.21 %) negative change in the study area.

Other cereals

Including rice and wheat the study area produces other cereals in a less amount such as barley and maize. The spatial distribution of other cereals in the study region shows that it covers only 0.13 percent cultivated area in 2005-06 which has recorded a slow decrease of 0.05 percent with negative change of -0.08 percent. The low concentration of other cereals is due to low yields, peoples focusing on cash crops like sugarcane, etc.

Total Pulses

The pulses deserve spatial attention in the food cultivation in the study area. Pulses have a high content of Protein. Pulses are Kharif as well as Rabi crop and the chief pulses grown in the study area e.g. Black gram, Moong, Lentil, Gram, Pea, and Toor. The distribution pattern of pulses is 17059 hectares (3.21%) in 2005-06 which has recorded a negative growth rate of 0.75% in the cultivated area. The cultivated area under total pulses is 13400 hectares (2.46%) in 2015-16.

Sugarcane

Sugarcane is one of the important cash crops in the study area. The total cultivated area under sugarcane production was 72233 hectares (13.58%) during 1993-94 which has increased to 87847 hectares in 2005-16 (16.15%) with the change of 2.57%. Because of the favorable condition in the study area and proper sources of irrigation, the cultivated area under sugarcane has increased during the decade.

Total Vegetables

The vegetable crops are cultivated in every season. The main vegetable crops in the study area are potato, onion, tomato, cabbage, chilly, cauliflower, coriander, etc. Vegetables share a very small portion of total cultivated land. The total cultivated area under vegetables was 18345 hectares (3.45%) during 2005-06 which decreased to 11079 hectares (2.04%).

Conclusion

This study shows the changes in land use and cropping pattern in Bareilly district. The land use of the study area has been analyzed for a period of twenty-two years from 1994-95 to 2016-17 and cropping pattern analysis has been done for the period of 2005-2015. In this study, we found that the area under forest cover has increased but only 0.01 percent during 1994-95 to 2016-17. The share of forest cover in the total rural reported area was 0.06 percent in 1994-05 which has increased to 0.07 percent after twenty-two years. The main reason behind the less forest cover in this region is rapidly growing population which encourages deforestation for more built-up and agricultural land. On the other hand, Area not available for cultivation and Fallow land has decreased which indicate that people has been converting this type of land to cultivated or built up land for their accordance. Net sown area has increased with the change of 0.98 percent due to the population pressure on land. The cropping pattern of the study area shows that only sugarcane and wheat crops recorded positive change with the change of 1.31 percent and 2.57 percent respectively. The increased area under sugarcane crop indicates that farmers are focusing on cash crop in the study area. The cultivated area under other crops like Rice, Barley, The tide, Millets, maize, pulses, oilseeds, and vegetables are decreased. The area under Fodder and miscellaneous crops has also shown positive change. Changes in social, technological and environmental can effect substantial changes in land use cropping pattern of the study area. The government should take some initiatives in the study are like expanding irrigation facilities, providing imported varieties of seeds, improvement in road network for the betterment of Rural Livelihood.

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